

Table 8: Shared positive rankings of statements

Stmt. No.	Statement	Theme 1 Intrinsically Motivated	Theme 2 Altruistic Leaning	Theme 3 Sales vs. Fiduciary	Consensus Rank
36	I feel my role is sales-oriented because I have to sell myself to FCs ¹ and sell myself to clients.	2	2	5	24
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	3	2	4	25
3	Because of my workload, I sometimes worry about the possibility of important things falling through the cracks.	4	0	4	32
31	As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	5	3	0	33

¹ 'FCs' refers to internal colleagues who are based in local branches that refer their prospects to advisors (PCAs) for participation in the advisory program.